

Acid-base Behaviour of Some Indicators in Mixed Solvents

Somesh Chakrabarti and S. Aditya

The pK 's of indicators, methyl orange, bromocresol green and thymol blue have been determined spectrophotometrically in dioxane-water and methanol-water media. The change in pK 's when the organic component is added to water has been analysed in terms of the property of the medium (basicity and also ion-solvent interaction) using Hepler equation for calculating the electrostatic contributions.

The dissociation of acids and bases of different charge-types changes in different manner in mixed aqueous solvents. In case of an acid of the uncharged-type, the pK value increases in aqueous-alcohol or aqueous-dioxan solvents. However, for the charged type acids the pK decreases on addition of alcohol or dioxan to an aqueous solution of the acid. At higher percentage of the organic component, the pK value often passes through a minimum. In recent years Bates and his coworkers^{1,1a}, de-Ligny and his coworkers² and Reynaud³ have reported the dissociation constants of many acids and bases in methanol-water and ethanol-water systems.

In this paper we report on the dissociation constants of some indicators in mixed aqueous solvents. Our interest in indicators stems from the fact that not only the investigation will furnish some more data for examining the role of solvent on the pK 's but that the pK 's in themselves are of analytical importance. For very few indicators pK 's in solvents other than those in water have been reported. Actually we needed the pK values of indicators in mixed-aqueous solvents in our programme for the determination of the dissociation constant of HSO_4^- ion using the method of Singleterry and Klotz⁴.

The indicator equilibrium in solution may be written as $HIn \rightleftharpoons H^+ + In^-$ and the corresponding constant as $K_{In} = \frac{a_{H^+} \cdot a_{In^-}}{a_{HIn}}$ where 'a' stands for activity. In other words,

$$pK_{In} = pH - \log \frac{C_{In^-}}{C_{HIn}} - \log f_{In^-} \quad (f \text{ stands for the activity coefficient}). \quad (1)$$

C_{In^-}/C_{HIn} can be estimated spectrophotometrically from the following relation,

$$\frac{C_{In^-}}{C_{HIn}} = \frac{d - d_1}{d_2 - d} \quad (a)$$

where d is the measured optical density of the indicator solution at the experimental pH and d_1 and d_2 are the optical densities of the indicator solution (of the same strength) in acid

1. R. G. Bates, *Chemistry and Industry* (Japan) 1965, 18, 680.
- 1a. M. Paabo, R. G. Bates and R. A. Robinson, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, 70, 247.
2. C. L. de-Ligny, *Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1960, 79, 731; 1961, 80, 725.
3. M. Rene Reynaud, *C.R. Acad. Sc. Paris*, 1966, Serie C 263, 105.
4. C. R. Singleterry and I. M. Klotz, "Electrolytic Solutions".
R. H. Stokes and R. A. Robinson, Butterworths. London, 2nd edn., 1959, p. 435.

and alkali forms (unionised and ionised forms) respectively. The activity coefficients have been calculated using the Debye-Huckel extended equation $Az_i^2 \sqrt{\mu}/(1 + \sqrt{\mu})$, where A is the constant dependent on temperature and the dielectric constant and μ is the ionic strength. Equation (1) may be put into the form,

$$-\log C_{H^+} + \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} = pK_{In} + \log \frac{C_{In^-}}{C_{HI_n}} \quad (2)$$

When the pH required for the determination is low (< 4) the hydrogen ion concentration can well be adjusted with perchloric acid. The left hand terms of equation, 2, can be plotted against $\log C_{In^-}/C_{HI_n}$ to get pK_{In} .

In cases, where the higher pH is to be maintained buffers have been used. For such solution we have also the equilibrium for the weak acid used and accordingly

$$pK_a + \log C_{A^-}/C_{HA} = pK_{In} + \log C_{In^-}/C_{HI_n} \quad (3)$$

pK_a , C_{A^-} and C_{HA} are the corresponding terms for the acid and its salt used in the buffer. Here again, the left hand terms may be plotted against $\log C_{In^-}/C_{HI_n}$ to get pK_{In} .

EXPERIMENTAL

Thymol blue used in the work was Reanal (Hungary), bromocresol green a BDH product and Methyl orange E. Merck make. Dioxane (B.D.H. Analar) and Methanol (B.D.H. Analar) were used after purification. Analar perchloric acid was used in the work. For higher pH 's acetic acid, sodium acetate buffers were used. The pK values of acetic acid in dioxane-water and methanol water were taken from the values given by Harned *et al.*^{5a,b,c}, and Bacarella *et al.*⁶.

The optical densities (O.D.) were measured at 25° with a Beckman DU spectrophotometer. The O.D. readings in duplicate experiments checked within 0.5%. The pH 's of the solutions were estimated from the amount of perchloric acid added and the theoretically calculated values of the activity coefficient of the hydrogen ion. In a number of cases the pH 's have also been measured with a glass electrode following the method of van Uitert *et al.*⁷ taking into account the necessary correction factors. For pH -measurements a battery-operated Cambridge Bench type pH -meter was used. All the measurements were made at 25°.

RESULTS

The pK_{In} values for methyl orange and thymol blue indicators were determined with the help of equation, 2, and that for Bromocresol green by using equation 3. The quantities required for extrapolations are reproduced in Tables 1, 2(a), 2(b), 3(a) and 3(b).

5a. H. S. Harned, G. L. Kazanjian, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1912.

5b. H. S. Harned, L. D. Fallon; *ibid.*, 1939, 61, 2377.

5c. H. S. Harned, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1938, 43, 275.

6. A. L. Bacarella, E. Grunwald, H. P. Marshall and E. L. Purdie, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, 20, 747.

7. L. G. Van Uitert, C. G. Hass, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 451.

TABLE 1

Methyl orange Dioxane-water medium

Percentage of Dioxane (w/w)							
20	(a)	1.80	2.20	2.60	3.00	3.40	3.80
	(b)	-1.0483	-0.717	-0.365	0.079	0.480	0.779
40	(a)	1.80	2.20	2.60	3.00	3.40	
	(b)	-0.949	-0.366	0.063	0.573	1.172	
60	(a)	1.40	1.80	2.20	2.60	3.00	
	(b)	-1.235	-0.664	-0.138	0.269	0.692	
80	(a)	2.14	2.196	2.26	2.34	2.44	
	(b)	-1.573	-1.371	-1.245	-1.038	-0.317	

Note : (a) = $-\log C_{H^+}$ (b) $\log C_{In} - /C_{HIIn} - \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}}$

TABLE 2(a)

Thymol blue in Dioxane-water mixture

Percentage of Dioxane						
20	(a)	1.93	1.98	2.01	2.04	2.09
	(b)	0.1905	0.2286	0.2580	0.3009	0.3588
40	(a)	2.28	2.35	2.41	2.51	2.59
	(b)	0.2948	0.3794	0.4182	0.5164	0.6070
60	(a)	2.80	2.82	2.84	2.85	2.87
	(b)	0.1797	0.2351	0.2462	0.2534	0.2825

TABLE 2(b)

Thymol Blue in Methanol-water mixture

Percentage of Methanol (w/w)							
20	(a)	1.89		1.93	1.96	2.00	2.04
	(b)	0.1581		0.1694	0.1911	0.2329	0.2638
40	(a)	2.20	2.26	2.34	2.40	2.52	2.82
	(b)	0.4127	0.4617	0.4990	0.5502	0.6628	0.8851
60	(a)	2.34	2.47	2.54	2.73	2.93	
	(b)	0.3246	0.4541	0.5385	0.7144	0.9002	
80	(a)	2.56	2.61	2.69	2.72	2.86	
	(b)	0.1673	0.2077	0.3619	0.3804	0.5421	

TABLE 3(a)

Bromo-cresol green in Dioxane-water mixture

Percentage of Dioxane							
20	(i)	4.60	4.90	5.20	5.50		5.80
	(ii)	-0.690	-0.385	-0.107	0.217		0.477
45	(i)	5.20	5.50	5.80	6.10	6.40	6.70
	(ii)	-1.136	-0.823	-0.544	-0.222	0.078	0.380
70	(i)	6.70	7.00	7.30	7.60	7.90	8.20
	(ii)	-1.393	-1.011	-0.699	-0.334	-0.005	0.301
82	(i)	9.50	9.57	9.60	9.64		9.70
	(ii)	-0.303	-0.214	-0.184	-0.144		-0.029

Note : (i) $pK_A + \log C_A^- / C_{HA}$ (ii) $\log C_{In^-} / C_{HI_n}$

TABLE 3(b)

Bromo-cresol green in Methanol-water mixture.

Percentage of Methanol (w/w)						
16.47	(i)	4.50	4.55	4.60	4.65	4.70
	(ii)	-0.623	-0.588	-0.535	-0.482	-0.424
34.47	(i)	4.75	4.80	4.85	4.90	4.95
	(ii)	-0.691	-0.652	-0.575	-0.483	-0.420
54.20	(i)	5.20	5.30	5.40	5.50	5.60
	(ii)	-0.586	-0.483	-0.396	-0.282	-0.208
75.94	(i)	5.80	5.90	6.00	6.10	6.20
	(ii)	-0.589	-0.473	-0.405	-0.273	-0.117

The necessary extrapolations were made graphically to find the pK_{In} values of the indicators in respective solvents. The extrapolated values of pK_{In} in mixed solvents designated as $(pK_{In})_s$ are reported in Tables 4(a) and 4(b) along with the dielectric constants for the mixed solvents. The pK_{In} in water also has been included in the table. In column VI, the values of ΔpK_{In} i.e., $(pK_{In})_s - (pK_{In})_w$ have been included.

The values of (pK_{In}) reported are accurate within ± 0.02 units in media containing upto 60% by weight of the organic component above which the error may be as high as ± 0.04 units.

TABLE 4(a)

pK_{In} values in Dioxane-water mixture at 25° for different indicators.

Name of the indicator	(<i>pK_{In}</i>) _w	Percentage of Dioxane	Dielectric constant (ϵ)	1/ ϵ	(<i>pK_{In}</i>) _s	ΔpK_{In}	(ΔG_0) _{obs} (KCal. mole ⁻¹)	(ΔG_0) _{t(others)} KCal mole ⁻¹
Thymol blue	1.70	20	61	0.0164	1.74	0.04	0.055	0.766
		40	43	0.0233	2.00	0.30	0.409	0.667
		60	26	0.0385	2.60	0.90	1.227	0.488
Bromo Cresol green	4.68	20	61	0.0164	5.28	0.60	0.818	1.497
		45	38.6	0.0259	6.30	1.62	2.210	2.197
		70	17.7	0.0565	7.95	3.27	4.460	2.215
		82	9.0	0.1111	9.75	5.07	6.915	0.689
Methyl orange	3.52	20	61	0.0164	2.95	-0.57	-0.777	-0.060
		40	43	0.0233	2.54	-0.98	-1.337	-1.062
		60	26	0.0385	2.38	-1.14	-1.555	-2.254
		80		0.1111	2.52	-1.00	-1.364	-6.718

TABLE 4(b)

Name of the Indicator	Percentage of Methanol	Dielectric constant (ϵ)	1/ ϵ	(<i>pK_{In}</i>) _s	ΔpK_{In}	(ΔG_0) _{obs} (KCal mole ⁻¹)	(ΔG_0) _{t(others)} (KCal mole ⁻¹)
Thymol blue	20	66.99	0.0143	1.75	0.05	0.068	0.918
	40	60.94	0.0164	1.82	0.12	0.164	0.878
	60	51.67	0.0193	2.02	0.32	0.436	0.554
	80	42.60	0.0235	2.40	0.70	0.955	1.203
Methyl orange	20	3.17	-0.35	-0.477	0.376
	40	2.67	-0.85	-1.159	-0.439
	60	2.22	-1.30	-1.773	-1.655
	80	...		2.27	-1.25	-1.705	-1.440
Bromo-Cresol green	16.47	71.4	0.0140	5.08	0.40	0.544	1.398
	34.47	63.4	0.0158	5.31	0.63	0.859	1.584
	54.4	54.4	0.0184	5.81	1.13	1.538	2.073
	75.94	44.2	0.0226	6.32	1.64	2.234	2.460

In figure 1, $(\Delta pK_{In})_{obs}$ has been plotted against weight-percentage of the organic solvent (methanol and dioxan). The pK 's for bromocresol green and thymol blue increase on addition of the organic component while that for methyl orange decreases and passes through

FIG. 1

a minimum and then increases. Similar curve has been reported by Bates and his co-workers¹ in case of methyl orange in methanol-water solvent and is expected as methyl orange is an indicator acid-base pair of the type HA^+ , $\overset{\ominus}{A}$. Thymol blue and bromocresol green are of the type, $H\overset{\ominus}{A}$, $\overset{\ominus}{A}$. (For comparison we have incorporated Bates' data on Methyl orange in our table).

It may be interesting to analyse the total $(\Delta pK_{In})_{obs}$ in terms of the electrostatic contribution and those of other types, thus putting $RT(\Delta pK_{In})_{obs} = \Delta G^0_{t(el)} + \Delta G^0_{t(others)}$. Paabo *et al.* and also Bates¹ have termed $\Delta G^0_{t(others)}$ as $\Delta G^0_{t(basicity)}$ thus attributing the difference between the observed free energy of transfer and the free energy of transfer due to the electrostatic contribution to the free energy associated with the basicity of the solvent.

Although basicity of the solvent is possibly the major contributing factor, ion-solvent term as also other interactions cannot be neglected and so we prefer to use for the difference of $\Delta G_{obs}^0 - \Delta G_{t(el)}^0$, the term $\Delta G_{t(others)}^0$. The free energy of transfer due to the electrostatic contribution can be calculated using Helper equation⁸. There are, however, a number of difficulties associated with the calculation of the electrostatic contribution. In choosing the value of the dielectric constant of the solvent, it cannot justifiably be taken to be the same as that for the bulk of the medium. On the other hand there is hardly any equation that could quantitatively describe the value of the dielectric constant in the regions extending from the vicinity of the ion to the bulk of the medium. The other uncertainty is the value of the ionic radius to be used in the calculations.

In our calculation we have used $r_{H^+} = 0.86 \text{ \AA}^{(9)}$ and $r_A^- = 6.0, 7.8$ and 8.2 \AA for bromocresol green, methyl orange and thymolblue ions respectively. The r_A^- 's have been calculated on the basis of the molecular structure using the bond distances from the table giving the data¹⁰. The indicator ions are large and as such not solvated. The values of $\Delta G_{t(others)}^0$ (the difference of $\Delta G_{t}^0(\text{obs.}) - \Delta G_{t}^0(\text{el.})$) have been given in Tables 4a and 4b. Figure II shows

FIG II

a graphical presentation of $(\Delta G_{t}^0)_{others}$ vs. composition of the solvent. Same trend is observed in all the cases.

The authors wish to thank the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, Government of India for a financial grant.

Department of Applied Chemistry,
Calcutta University,
Calcutta-9, India.

Received July 18, 1968.
Revised MSS received July 2, 1969.

8. L. G. Hepler, *Austr. J. Chem.*, 1964, 17, 587.
9. R. G. Bates and R. A. Robinson in *Chemical Physics of Ionic solutions*, Ed. B. E. Conway and R. G. Barradas, John Wiley and Sons Inc., 1966, p. 234.
10. Tables of Interatomic distances and configuration in molecules Special Publication No. 11. The Chemical Society London, 1958.